

Abstract: In Special Relativity it is well established that relatively moving observers measure different times for an observed event. However, it is always assumed that relatively moving observers agree on their relative velocity, expressed as v/c , even though velocity is a function of time. Special Relativity can be reinterpreted by adding an assumption that space is invariant. Relatively moving observers will then find different relative velocities and time variance will be shown to be a result of how measurements are referenced at the quantum level.

For a particle of rest mass m_0 : , momentum four-vectors show a momentum at rest of $p = m_0 \cdot c$: suggesting some internal movement at the speed of light c . It will be assumed here that time intervals are defined by particle clocks, such as the decay time of a muon, and that particles are comprised of a fundamental quantum moving in an orbit at light speed. For this discussion, the fundamental quantum will be assumed to be an inert, massless point, moving in a circular orbit transverse to any translational movement of a particle. The rest frame of a particle is not a rest frame for the quantum since the quantum is continually moving.

FIG 1 shows wavelength, time and mass for a particle translating distance D . λ_0 : is the at-rest wavelength - the distance the quantum moves on a circular orbit when the particle is at rest. λ_Q : is the resultant total path of the quantum when the particle translates distance D . The second triangle shows times associated with the event. t_0 : is the time period for a cycle of the quantum orbit. t_Q : is total event time as measured by the movement of the quantum. Since the quantum is moving at the speed of light c :

$$\lambda_0 = c \cdot t_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_Q = c \cdot t_Q$$

The observed event is the particle moving distance D . **The speed will be labelled v_{PA} : to distinguish it as the speed of particle P as measured by an observer in a reference frame A.** If the time for the event is defined by total quantum movement, the time is t_Q : and the speed of the moving particle is:

$$v_{PA} = \frac{D}{t_Q} :$$

Squaring and substituting for D :

$$v_{PA}^2 = \frac{D^2}{t_Q^2} = \frac{(c \cdot t_Q)^2 - (c \cdot t_0)^2}{t_Q^2} : \text{ leads to } \frac{v_{PA}^2}{c^2} = 1 - \frac{t_0^2}{t_Q^2} : \text{ and } t_Q = \frac{t_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_{PA}^2}{c^2}}} :$$

which is the usual relativistic time transform.

This shows that time variance can result from the way measurements are referenced at the quantum level, with space invariance being assumed. This picture is too simplistic; for example, the paper **Electron Geometry** shows that an electron is comprised of a quantum traversing a toroidal orbit.

Another speed v_{AP} : can be defined as the speed that reference frame A moves as measured from the rest frame of particle P. The quantum moves within the particle rest frame and defines the time t_0 : . The speed of reference frame A as observed from the rest frame of particle P is:

$$v_{AP} = \frac{D}{t_0} :$$

Squaring and substituting for D:

$$v_{AP}^2 = \frac{D^2}{t_0^2} = \frac{(c \cdot t_Q)^2 - (c \cdot t_0)^2}{t_0^2} : \quad \text{leads to} \quad \frac{v_{AP}^2}{c^2} = \frac{t_Q^2}{t_0^2} - 1 :$$

Further manipulation gives the relativistic time transform:

$$t_0 = \frac{t_Q}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{v_{AP}^2}{c^2}}} :$$

Due to space invariance $D = v_{PA} \cdot t_Q = v_{AP} \cdot t_0$:

v_{AP} : is seen to be greater than v_{PA} : since t_0 : is less than t_Q : , and can be greater than light speed with high speed particles. Asymmetry in speed determinations by relatively moving observers is compatible with there being an absolute rest frame of reference, which modern data suggest is the rest frame of the Cosmic Microwave Background radiation.

Manipulating the above results leads to the following relations between speeds:

$$v_{AP} = \frac{v_{PA}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_{PA}^2}{c^2}}} : \quad v_{PA} = \frac{v_{AP}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{v_{AP}^2}{c^2}}} : \quad 1 + \frac{v_{AP}^2}{c^2} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{PA}^2}{c^2}} :$$

The third triangle in FIG 1 shows mass. Since mass varies relativistically in the same manner as time, the momentum \mathbf{p} can readily be written in the conventional formula using m_0 : as the rest mass. Using the new relationships presented above leads to equal momentum expressions of the same form in the two frames of reference:

$$p = \frac{m_0 \cdot v_{PA}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_{PA}^2}{c^2}}} = m_0 \cdot v_{AP} = m_Q \cdot v_{PA} :$$

Using squares for convenience:

$$\text{Since } v_{PA}^2 = \frac{D^2}{t_Q^2} : \text{ then } t_Q^2 = \frac{t_0^2}{1 - \frac{v_{PA}^2}{c^2}} = \frac{t_0^2}{1 - \frac{D^2}{c^2 \cdot t_0^2}} : \text{ which gives } t_Q^2 = \frac{D^2}{c^2} + t_0^2 :$$

$$\text{Since } v_{AP}^2 = \frac{D^2}{t_0^2} : \text{ then } t_0^2 = \frac{t_Q^2}{1 + \frac{v_{AP}^2}{c^2}} = \frac{t_Q^2}{1 + \frac{D^2}{c^2 \cdot t_0^2}} : \text{ which gives } t_Q^2 = \frac{D^2}{c^2} + t_0^2 :$$

The time relationships are defined by the speed of light.

Relativistic reasoning can be extended to a photon. For this discussion, λ_0 : the transverse photon wavelength, will be taken to be equal to λ_D : the distance the photon translates during one period.

This equality is used for illustration and is not substantiated by any results presented here. It will be assumed that the photon is comprised of a massless, inert quantum following the resulting helical path. The quantum will be assumed to travel at speed s , rather than light speed c . As shown in FIG 2:

$$\lambda_0 = s \cdot t_0 : \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_Q = s \cdot t_Q = \sqrt{2} \cdot \lambda_D : \text{ since } \lambda_D = \lambda_0 :$$

The observed event is a photon P translating distance λ_D at speed $u_{PA} = c$: . If time for the event is taken to be total quantum travel time t_Q : then:

$$u_{PA} = c = \frac{\lambda_D}{t_Q} : \quad \text{and quantum speed } s = \frac{\lambda_Q}{t_Q} = \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot \lambda_D}{t_Q} = \sqrt{2} \cdot c :$$

Squaring u_{PA} and substituting for λ_D :

$$u_{PA}^2 = \frac{\lambda_D^2}{t_Q^2} = \frac{(s \cdot t_Q)^2 - (s \cdot t_0)^2}{t_Q^2} : \quad \text{leads to} \quad \frac{u_{PA}^2}{s^2} = 1 - \frac{t_0^2}{t_Q^2} :$$

Further manipulation gives the relativistic time transform with speed s :

$$t_Q = \frac{t_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u_{PA}^2}{s^2}}} : \quad \text{leading to} \quad t_Q = \sqrt{2} \cdot t_0 : \quad \text{since } u_{PA} = c : \text{ and } s = \sqrt{2} \cdot c :$$

The speed u_{AP} : of reference frame A as observed from the photon P frame of reference is:

$$u_{AP} = \frac{\lambda_D}{t_0} = \sqrt{2} \cdot \frac{\lambda_D}{t_Q} = \sqrt{2} \cdot c = s :$$

The third triangle in FIG 2 shows equivalent mass. Assuming equivalent mass varies relativistically the same as time:

$$m_Q = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{c^2}{s^2}}} = \sqrt{2} \cdot m_0 : \quad \text{leads to} \quad m_0 = \frac{m_Q}{\sqrt{2}} :$$

This shows a transverse rest mass for a photon, which might correspond to a virtual photon when there is no translation. Zero rest mass for the photon occurs when a massless quantum, which normally traverses the photon orbit, is totally at rest. Again, this picture is probably too simplistic, but it suggests that relativistic reasoning can be applied to photons.

In the paper **Electron Geometry** an expression for the Planck constant was presented:

$$h_{defr} := \left(\frac{\sqrt{2.0} \cdot 2.0 \cdot \pi \cdot r}{T1 \cdot 1.0E+12} \right) : \quad \text{Planck constant with r and T1}$$

where T1=2.729336 : is the Cosmic Microwave Background temperature as measured from the Solar System frame of reference. r was found to be 2.035×10^{-19} meter, and is proposed to be the radius of a massless, inert quantum..

Calculating the equivalent mass of a hypothetical virtual photon of wavelength $2 \cdot \pi \cdot R$: gives:

$$m_0 = \frac{m_Q}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{h}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot R \cdot c} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot R \cdot c} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot r}{T1 \cdot 1.0E+12} = \frac{r}{R \cdot T1 \cdot 1.0E+12} :$$

The square root of 2 factor in the Planck constant, which cancels here, led to the most accurate match of physical constants determined for **Electron Geometry**.

An electron can now be pictured as a photon state in which a virtual photon has acquired a second orbit, setting the quantum on a toroidal path. If a toroidal electron is set in motion along the axis of the toroidal path, the motion is transverse to the constituent photon and the electron's mass varies relativistically in the same manner as the relativistic transverse transform of photon energy. The rest mass m_0 : is the same as the equivalent mass of a photon of Compton wavelength $2 \cdot \pi \cdot R_C$: where R_C : is the Compton radius. In the paper **Electron Geometry**, the Compton radius is shown to be much smaller than the radius of the constituent virtual photon, according to:

$$R_C = \frac{2 \cdot \beta e}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} + \alpha \right)} : \quad \text{and} \quad \beta e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot R_C \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} + \alpha \right) :$$

where βe : is the radius of the first orbit of the photon comprising the electron. From the above discussion of virtual photons, the equivalent mass of the electron's virtual photon would be:

$$m\beta e = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{h}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot \beta e \cdot c} :$$